

Interpreting UKRI Environmental Sustainability Guidance for the Digital Humanities v2.1

digital humanities climate coalition

Interpreting UKRI Environmental Sustainability Guidance for the Digital Humanities (v2.1)

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Change log March 2026: substantial update from [v1](#) focused on integrating the second UKRI [Environmental Sustainability Strategy](#).

Funders set expectations around research practice. This extends to how research impacts wider society and the environment. UK Research and Innovation (UKRI) have published a [sustainability strategy](#) and is a signatory of a [cross-sector environmental sustainability concordat](#), and in December 2024, the [AHRC Research Funding Guide](#) was updated to include for the first time [a statement on environmental responsibility](#).

For net zero goals to be achieved, those involved in research need to play their part. However, funder expectations have not yet been matched by resources that help applicants adapt their research practices to support environmental and ecological sustainability.

This document offers interpretations of current guidance on research and innovation practice and directs readers to advice on operationalising sustainable approaches. Our interpretations draw on the [Digital Humanities Climate Coalition Toolkit](#), an extensive and evolving resource that provides guidance on making research practices more environmentally responsible. As such, the document is aimed primarily at Digital Humanities practitioners, researchers, technicians, curators, software engineers, and related professionals, though we anticipate it will be useful to those working across the entire UKRI remit. The purpose of the document is to inspire confidence that climate conscious work is aligned with funder priorities, that environmental actions are integral to

research excellence, and that pushing back against impediments to action is justified and justifiable.

We believe this document is needed because despite a long history of environmental policy at the international level, environmental policy relating to research is relatively new. The development of these new policies mirrors the heightened focus on the connections between climate change and our dependence on digital technologies. While many view technological change as a source of potential solutions to environmental challenges, it is increasingly understood that the environmental cost of digital technology is significant.

Good estimates are very hard to come by, but as a ballpark figure, digital technology may make up about 4-5% of our global carbon emissions.¹ Carbon emissions associated with digital technology are also projected to grow significantly, accelerated by the electricity demand of artificial intelligence systems ([International Energy Agency, 2025](#)). Beyond emissions, these technologies depend on highly extractive supply chains that deplete natural and abiotic resources. And while the economic and technological benefits of these energetic and extractive practices are centralised, the ecological and social costs are externalised, disproportionately affecting communities in the global south through resource depletion and the import and disposal of electronic waste.

The use of digital technologies in research contributes to environmental degradation in various ways, from our everyday working practices to our use of high-performance computing research facilities. Research funding bodies such as UKRI place the onus on applicants to understand and evaluate the environmental cost and sustainability of their own digital projects. Their policies, plans, and objectives have the potential to address the current lack of data on the environmental impacts of research, overcome ingrained working practices that limit sustainable research design, and strengthen advocacy by anchoring it within established institutions. There is an urgent need to realise that potential. We

¹ [Lannelongue et al. \(2024\)](#) estimate that the digital sector contributes 4.75% of UK GHG emissions. In an often cited paper from 2021, [Freitag et al.](#) estimated that in 2020 global emissions from Information Communication Technology (ICT) could be around 2.1%–3.9%. The same paper also estimated that if ICT emissions were to remain stable, and global emissions to decrease in line with 1.5 degrees, by 2026 ICT would be accounting for about 5% of the global carbon footprint. However, neither of these assumptions is a good reflection of the past five years: we have seen growth in both ICT emissions and total global emissions. [Stern et al. \(2025\)](#) include enabled carbon savings in key sectors and conclude that AI is net carbon negative, but [Joshi \(2026\)](#) finds evidence for ‘AI for sustainability’ to be weak and misleading.

therefore interpret the increasing emphasis on environmental responsibility in UKRI policy and funding guidance as a call to action, as well as a basis for holding UKRI to account for delivering on their commitments. This document is part of that work and we hope it emboldens Digital Humanities practitioners, researchers, technicians, curators, software engineers, and related professionals to embed environmental responsibility into their research design without fear that their actions will be perceived as compromising research excellence.

UKRI Environmental Sustainability Strategy

In 2025 UKRI published its second [Environmental Sustainability Strategy](#) (updating its 2020 strategy). The document sets out a five-year plan detailing how UKRI intends to lead by example in environmental sustainability. The most notable target in the strategy is UKRI’s commitment to a **50% reduction of greenhouse emission by 2030** (compared to their 2017/18 baseline). And whilst this commitment is restricted to UKRI operations, a funder commitment of this nature provides justification for applicants to act on environmental sustainability, including in their use of digital technologies.

UKRI Environmental Strategy	
Wording	Interpretation
“Funding of any new infrastructure investments will require minimising operational costs and exploitation of natural resources, as well as being capable of withstanding the increasing impacts of climate change for the duration of their operations”	Here UKRI are making an economic case for green investment: that reducing the environmental impact of our work can align with reducing overall costs, especially in preparing now for the impacts of climate change on research practice. Acting now will position you, your group, and/or your institution as an ideal partner for future infrastructure investments.
“We recognise that sustainability can relate to many different considerations including the quality and lifespan of products, how they are packaged, delivered and whether the products can be re-used, repaired, or recycled. UKRI considers all these elements as part of a ‘value for money’ definition”	Here UKRI are redefining what constitutes ‘value for money’ in funding decisions. Increased monetary costs are justifiable if they reduce environmental costs. To underscore this point in relation to digital technologies, elsewhere the Strategy notes that “collaboration [...] must promote circular economy principles, particularly extending

	the life of research equipment and increasing use of refurbished or re-build equipment”.
“Some of our scientific equipment and computing infrastructure are significant consumers of energy and other natural resources, such as water. Future investments and procurement of such equipment must consider these impacts as an element of the assessments, as well as their impact on the emissions trajectory of UKRI”	UKRI are here setting an example for the research and innovation community by including infrastructures that support research in their greenhouse gas reduction targets. UKRI are demonstrating that the first step is to own the problem. Those wishing to do the same may consult DHCC Toolkit guidance on methods for measuring the carbon footprint of computationally intensive research .
“This will include the requirement to share equipment funded (or partially funded) by UKRI and to provide meaningful access for the wider science community, as well as extending the lifecycle of equipment”	UKRI will develop new requirements for environmental sustainability by 2029, central to which is this commitment to mandates on resource sharing. Developing partnerships and policies in advance of this change, taking models such as RICHeS as inspiration, will enable you, your group, and/or your institution to anticipate this change.
“Objective: use UKRI leverage as a funder and collaborator to drive environmentally sustainable principles in research and innovation practice [...] UKRI will improve the net benefit of research by making environmentally and resource-conscious decisions in the R&I that we undertake and fund, while maintaining research excellence”	Here UKRI continues a commitment made in their previous Environmental Strategy to change the process of applying for grants to align with sustainability goals. We can expect UKRI to use funding schemes to drive best practice. The DHCC Toolkit includes specific guidance on grant writing .
“To support colleagues to embed environmental sustainability, we will deliver training to improve environmental literacy and will enable and support the sharing of knowledge and good practice within our organisation and across the R&I sector. UKRI will regularly communicate sustainability progress through impactful stories, inspiring employees, clarifying expectations, and celebrating collective achievement”	Here UKRI demonstrate a commitment to adapt their working practices to engage with environmental sustainability. Making time in your project to set expectations for sustainable practice and to celebrate sustainability achievements aligns with UKRI goals. The DHCC Toolkit contains guidance on day-to-day working practices , as well as on advocating for those changes to be made within your institution.
“Our commitment as a signatory to the Concordat for the Environmental Sustainability of Research and Innovation Practice shall	UKRI will use the Concordat to ensure a collective approach to research and innovation investment, best practice development, and knowledge sharing among

provide focus and direction for us to work with and align with the sector moving forward”	funders. In turn, those engaged in research are expected to understand the importance of the Concordat to UKRI, its operations, and its decision making.
“2027: design, develop and transfer the knowledge platform SPARKHub to a host for launch. SPARKHub is a resource to support the R&I community with practical solutions on improving the sustainability of their work. Short for Sustainable Practice and Research Knowledge Hub, it provides certification and guidance and is supported by multiple research funders”	UKRI will use the SPARKHub as a delivery mechanism for changing research and innovation practice. You, your group, and/or your institution will be expected to engage with the SPARKHub and use its guidance in project design and delivery.
“Objective: reduce business travel emissions while maintaining collaboration and outreach”	UKRI are here setting an example for the research and innovation community by committing to a climate-conscious approach toward travel. They pledge to implement a travel hierarchy with air travel as a last resort and a consideration of the value of in-person attendance. Those engaged in research and innovation should make similar considerations.

Responsible Innovation

UKRI’s Environmental Strategy falls under the umbrella of ‘[Responsible Innovation](#)’, which is understood to mean the careful consideration of, and action to address, the potential impacts of introducing a new product, service, process or business model. UKRI policy on innovation can often seem more relevant to scientists and engineers than individuals and groups working in the Digital Humanities. For example, existing guidance foregrounds the Engineering and Physical Sciences Research Council’s [Anticipate, Reflect, Engage, Act \(AREA\)](#) framework as a model for responsible innovation. However, innovation is at the heart of all research, and even the AREA framework can be usefully used to drive environmentally responsible innovation in the Digital Humanities.

EPSRC Anticipate, Reflect, Engage, Act Framework	
Wording	Interpretation
“Responsible research and innovation acknowledges that innovation can raise	Innovation is not just about products but also the environment in which products are

<p>questions and dilemmas, is often ambiguous in terms of purposes and motivations and unpredictable in terms of impacts, beneficial or otherwise”</p>	<p>produced: to innovate responsibly is to consider impact broadly. The DHCC Toolkit includes guidance on reducing the environmental impact of the research processes such as emails and videoconferencing. Responsible innovation can also be the basis for advocacy within your institution to cultivate environmentally sustainable working cultures.</p>
<p>“We expect our research community to [...] reflect on their own personal and collective motivations”</p>	<p>Responsible innovation is often framed in relation to external impacts but it is also about your identity. If you became involved in research to pursue new knowledge, do you really want this to risk threatening human life? The <i>Digital Humanities and the Climate Crisis: A Manifesto (2021)</i> – a document connected to the DHCC Toolkit – takes a confident and critical stance on the relationship between digital technologies, their materiality, and the particular environmental responsibility of individuals and groups working in the Digital Humanities. It is a framework for honouring your responsibility to the environment.</p>
<p>“We expect our research community to [...] enter into dialogue with the public and other stakeholders”</p>	<p>Public engagement is part of responsible innovation. The DHCC toolkit includes a growing number of case studies of how Digital Humanities practitioners, researchers, technicians, curators, software engineers, and related professionals have communicated, raised awareness of, and advocated for environmental responsibility.</p>

Ethical Research and Innovation

UKRI uses a variety of mechanisms to recognise and reward high-quality research. [This includes ethical research and innovation](#). UKRI guidance in this area – which links outwards to a range of documents – provides plenty of scope for Digital Humanities practitioners, researchers, technicians, curators, software engineers, and related professionals to

develop innovative research that embeds digital sustainability grounded in ethical good practice.

UKRI Ethical Research and Innovation Resource		
Document	Wording	Interpretation
UKRI position statement on funding ethical research	“The research and innovation community should seek, where possible, to enhance environmental sustainability through innovation and the adoption of environmentally sustainable research practices”	Innovation should not come at the expense of environmentally sustainable research practice. The DHCC Toolkit contains guidance on how to counter discourses of techno-optimism and techno-solutionism that create pressures to prioritise innovation at the expense of environmental responsibility, as well as detailed advice on various ways of working sustainably.
UKRI Policy on the governance of good research practice	“Research misconduct can take many forms, including [...] not observing legal, ethical and other requirements for [...] the protection of the environment”	Ignoring environmental protections is a form of misconduct. The DHCC Toolkit provides guidance on how to confront greenwashing and discourses of delay , practices that can be interpreted as not observing ethical responsibilities for the protection of the environment.
ESRC framework for research ethics	“Researchers, ROs and RECs should consider ethics issues throughout the lifecycle”	The lifecycle of a research project extends beyond the end of the project. The DHCC Toolkit provides various points of entry for those thinking about the environmental impact of a project after completion, including decisions around data archiving , sustainable web development , and procurement decisions .
Ethical Research and Innovation: ‘Roles and Responsibilities’	“Ensuring research is conducted ethically is a collective responsibility”	Humans live interdependent lives. Consider your responsibility to share your knowledge and experience with digital sustainability with colleagues and partners. Find your collaborators , help people learn , and acknowledge what you don’t know . You could even use your research to get involved in the work of organisations like the DHCC .

An Example UKRI Funding Call

Whilst funding guidance is relatively consistent across the UKRI research councils, subtle changes can create opportunities to embed digital sustainability in your response. The [UKRI Digital Research Technical Professional Skills NetworkPlus funding call](#) – a recent cross-council call related to the Digital Humanities – included sections on data management, responsible innovation, environmental sustainability, ethics and responsible research and innovation (RRI), and resource and cost justification. We use this call as an example of how to interpret a funding call in relation to digital technologies and environmental sustainability.

UKRI Digital Research Technical Professional Skills NetworkPlus 'What we're looking for'		
Section	Wording	Interpretation
Data Management	"[You] must adhere to UKRI open research policy"	When writing your funding application, consider the impact of any resources you publish to the web, whether (dynamic) websites, data, code, or software. The DHCC toolkit includes guidance on various 'lean' computational practices, including minifying website design , compressing images , reducing client side features , and minimal data publication .
Responsible innovation	"We are fully committed to develop and promote responsible research and innovation [...] through the way in which research and innovation is conducted and facilities are managed"	You are encouraged to foreground responsible research design, including environmental responsibility. Strengthen your application by showing how sustainability considerations and monitoring are embedded into project processes and activities. Even training an AI can be done responsibly, and the DHCC Toolkit contains advice on limiting the environmental impact of maximal computing activities .
Environmental Sustainability	"We expect you to embed careful consideration of environmental sustainability at all stages of the research and innovation process and throughout the lifetime of your NetworkPlus"	The call is looking for projects that enable UKRI to meet the ambitions of its environmental sustainability strategy. Be bold and design your response around environmental action. The DHCC includes guidance on how to develop research questions that support environmental action .

When applying for funding, look out for guidance that indicates which parts of your application are asking you to justify your project design with respect to environmental sustainability and responsible innovation. In the [UKRI Digital Research Technical Professional Skills NetworkPlus funding call](#), two sections provided opportunities to tease out how your project will meet these responsibilities.

UKRI Digital Research Technical Professional Skills NetworkPlus 'How to Apply'		
Section	Wording	Interpretation
Ethics and responsible research innovation (RRI)	“All awardees expect to adhere to the UKRI responsible innovation policies and guidance”	The funder is encouraging you to use this section of your application to explain how you will balance innovation with societal and environmental impacts. Innovative approaches to sustainable innovation are possible. The DHCC Toolkit provides guidance on how to frame responsible research as innovation .
Ethics and responsible research innovation (RRI)	“If you are collecting or using data, identify [...] any legal and ethical considerations of collecting, releasing or storing the data”	Legal and ethical considerations can include the Paris Climate Agreement and UKRI’s Environmental Sustainability Strategy . It can also refer to your own moral standards. Be bold and hold yourself to high standards: join the DHCC mailing list to receive invites to our monthly DHCC Community Calls where you can ask the community for advice on how they do it.
Resources and cost justification	“cost”	Costs can be financial, ecological and social. Each can be outlined in this section. Consider measuring the carbon emissions and environmental impact of your research: see the ‘Grant Writing’ section of the DHCC Toolkit for guidance. Consider engaging with and, where appropriate, resourcing local stakeholders to ensure impacts are socially and culturally sustainable.
Resources and cost justification	“Justify the application’s more costly resources, in particular [...] significant travel for field work or collaboration”	There is an environmental cost to travel. Justifying your travel decisions – including the travel you choose not to make – with regards to environmental considerations is an appropriate use of this section of the proposal. The DHCC Toolkit includes

		guidance on balancing travel with career stage and opportunity costs , benchmarking face-to-face work against online meetings , and ways to make the most out of unavoidable carbon intensive travel .
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